

Effect of 4 Weeks Hold Relax Stretching Technique versus Tendinous Pressure Technique on Calf Muscle Tone Along with Conventional Positional Stretching in Stroke Patients: A Randomized Controlled Trial

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Abstract

Background: Typically, the spasticity develops in calf muscles following stroke which leads equinovarus deformity of foot, limitation of range of ankle dorsiflexion causing difficulty in ambulation and maintaining balance. Poor balance and faulty gait can increase the risk of fall in stroke patient. So, it is important to reduce the calf muscles' spasticity for faster and effective recovery. Considering this as a prime need, the current study was planned to compare the effect of Hold-Relax Stretching technique and Tendinous Pressure technique on calf muscle tone in patients with stroke. **Materials and methods-** As per the selection criteria, 70 stroke patients (men and women) were selected and equally divided into two groups (Group A and Group B). Demographic data was collected along with the initial calf muscle tone on the Modified Ashworth Scale (MAS). Then, the 4 weeks intervention of Hold-Relax Stretching technique was given to Group A and Tendinous Pressure technique in Group B respectively. Calf muscle tone was reassessed on MAS and interpreted at the end of 4 weeks.

Result – The statistical analysis showed both the technique significantly effective in reducing the calf muscle tone on MAS at the end of 4 weeks intervention. However, Hold-Relax Stretching technique was found superior to Tendinous Pressure technique.

Conclusion: The calf muscle tone in stroke patients on modified Ashworth scale has reduced post intervention.

Key words –

Calf muscle, Tone, Hold-Relax Stretching, Stroke, Tendinous Pressure, Modified Ashworth Scale, Spasticity.

Introduction:

Stroke (cerebrovascular accident-CVA) is the sudden loss of neurological function caused by an interruption of the blood flow to the brain.^[1] Prevalence of stroke in India is 108 to 172/100,000 people per year.^[2] It leads to upper motor neuron lesion causing increase in muscle tone (Spasticity), hyper-reflexia and tightness of muscle etc. The prevalence of spasticity among stroke patients has been reported to be 27% at one month, 28% at three months, 23% and 43% at six months, and 34% at 18 months.^[3,4] Spasticity causes restricted range of motion of joint, muscle stiffness, pain and discomfort which make the patient difficult to perform any activity. Spasticity of calf muscle reduces the range of dorsiflexion at ankle joint causing difficulty in the gait activity and balance which ultimately increases the risk of fall in stroke patients.^[5,6,7]

Therefore, combating calf muscle stiffness and restoring its normal tone becomes crucial components of stroke rehabilitation. There are many techniques which are used to reduce the spasticity. Conventional Positional Stretching, Hold-Relax Stretching techniques and Tendinous Pressure are often used in clinical practice as they are easy to perform and less cost effective.

Positional stretching through weight bearing is well known and well accepted for its effect in reducing the spasticity. Weight-bearing acts as a prolonged stretch which helps to relax spastic muscles reduce its involuntary contractions and ultimately stimulating neuroplasticity.^[8,9]

Hold-Relax Stretching technique is one of the types of Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation (PNF) technique which can be used to increase flexibility and reduce tone of muscle by reflex relaxation. Dafda et al. (2021).^[10] and Suvarna et. al. (2016).^[11], have found positive impact of Hold-Relax Stretching technique in reducing the tone of spastic muscles.

Roods developed a technique for facilitation and inhibition of movement through various stimuli in the year 1950. The basic concept of Roods is the normalization of muscular tone by facilitation or inhibition via sensory cues. Tendinous Pressure is one of inhibitory technique of Rood approach which is used to reduce muscle tone. In this technique, manual pressure is applied to the tendinous insertion of the muscle or across long tendons to produce an inhibitory effect.

[11,12] Studies done by Marathe et al. (2020); [13] Gardas, et. al. (2020); [12] and Panda, et. al.(2023) [14] have notice tendinous pressure effective on tone reduction.

But there are dearth of literature which compares Hold-Relax Stretching technique and Tendinous Pressure technique along with conventional stretching techniques applied over calf muscle to reduce spasticity and normalize the muscle tone.

Therefore, the present study was conducted to compare the effect of 4 weeks of Hold Relax Stretching Technique and Tendinous Pressure Technique on Calf Muscle Tone in Stroke Patients.

Materials and Methods: An experimental study was conducted on 70 stroke patients (35 in each group). The inclusion criteria of the study were: - both genders; voluntary control grade 4 and above; Calf muscle spasticity of grade 1 and above on Modified Ashworth scale; patient with history of primary stroke; Mini Mental Scale Score more than 24. The exclusion criteria were: - uncooperative patients or those who were not willing to participate; patients with recent fracture of lower limb; patients with any musculoskeletal condition which was affecting ankle joint function; patients with hamstring tightness; patients with any neurological conditions other than stroke.

Treatment procedure: Prior to intervention, demographic data of all patients was collected and the grade of calf muscle tone (spasticity) was assessed by using Modified Ashworth Scale

Conventional Positional Stretching was given to all the patients of both groups. They were asked to stand on the wedge board (70° of inclination) with or without support for 10 min. The therapist was standing by the side of patient for safeguarding. [8,9]

Hold-Relax Stretching technique was intervened to the participants of group A and Tendinous Pressure technique for the participants of Group B respectively.

For Hold-Relax Stretching technique, the patient was placed in supine lying position with foot at the edge of treatment table and ankle with available range of dorsiflexion. Then the patient was asked to plantarflex the ankle and was asked to hold it for 10 seconds which was followed by 5 seconds of relaxation. After four repetition two minutes of relaxation was given. Then the next set of four repetition was conducted. The hold relax technique was intervened with the frequency of 4 repetition/set; 2 sets/session/day; 5 session/week for 4 weeks. [10,15]

For Tendinous Pressure technique, the patient was placed in prone lying position with foot at the edge of treatment table. The pressure was applied on calf muscle tendon (Tendo-Achilis) by the therapist's both thumb and maintained for 30 seconds. This procedure was repeated for four times with the interval of one minute. The frequency of Tendinous Pressure technique intervention was 4 repetitions/ session/day; 5 session/week for 4 weeks. [13,14]

At the end of four weeks intervention, the calf muscle tone was reassessed on Modified Ashworth's Scale.

Statistics:Data was analyzed with the statistical software, STATA, version 10.1, 2011.Descriptive statistics included summary measures like Mean, Standard Deviation (SD) for the quantitative variables while frequency and percentages were used to summarize the qualitative variables.Within-group, Pre and Post intervention mean values were compared by using paired t-test. Between-the-groups, Pre and Post intervention mean values were compared by using unpaired t-test.

p -value less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant for all the comparisons.

Result: This study included 70 subjects, 35 subjects in group A and 35 in group B.

Table no. 1: Age-wise distribution of participants in group A and group B

Age Range (years)	Number of Participants		Total
	Group A	Group B	
<40	2 (5.7%)	1 (2.9%)	3 (4.3%)
41-50	8 (22.9%)	8 (22.9%)	16 (22.9%)
51-60	14 (40.0%)	13 (37.1%)	27 (38.6%)
61 -70	8 (22.9%)	11 (31.4%)	19 (27.1%)
71-80	3 (8.6%)	2 (5.7%)	5 (7.1%)
Total	35 (100.0%)	35 (100.0%)	70 (100.0%)

Table no. 2: Gender wise distribution of participants in Group A and Group B.

Gender	Number of Participants		Total
	Group A	Group B	
Male	13 (37.1%)	11 (31.4%)	24 (34.3%)
Female	8 (62.9%)	8 (68.6%)	16 (65.7%)
Total	35 (100.0%)	35 (100.0%)	70 (100.0%)

Table no.3: Distribution of participants as per the side of involvement in Group A and Group B.

Side of involvement	Number of Participants		Total
	Group A	Group B	
Left. Side	20 (57.1%)	23(65.7%)	43(61.4%)

Right. Side	15(42.9%)	12 (34.3%)	27 (38.6%)
Total	35 (100.0%)	35 (100.0%)	70 (100.0%)

Table no. 4: Pre and post intervention Mean Score on Modified Ashworth's Scale with Std. Deviation of Calf muscle tone in Group A and Group B.

Assessment	Mean Score on Modified Ashworth's Scale with Std. Deviation		t-value	p-value
	Group A	Group B		
Pre-intervention	1.80±0.406	1.63±0.490	1.594	0.116
Post-intervention	0.89±0.471	1.23±0.426	-3.194	0.002
t-value	14.48	4.76		
p-value	<0.001	<0.001		

Discussion: The current study was conducted to find out the 4 weeks effect of Hold-Relax Stretching technique versus Tendinous Pressure technique on calf muscle tone along with Conventional Positional Stretching in stroke patients.

At the end of 4 weeks, both the techniques were found significantly effective in reducing the calf muscle tone on modified Ashworth's Scale.

In Group A, the Hold-Relax Stretching technique was found effective. The pre-intervention mean of Modified Ashworth's Scale score of group A was 1.8 and post-intervention it changed to 0.89. (p value <0.001).

The Hold-Relax Stretching technique primarily functions on the basis of neuromuscular mechanism that leads reciprocal inhibition followed by autogenic inhibition through inverse myotatic reflex.^[16-24] It triggers autogenic inhibitory mechanism by stimulation of Golgi tendon organ which causes reduction in muscle tension.^[18-24] Hold-Relax Stretching helps to slowly overcome the pathologically evolved tightness of the muscles due to the excessive firing of the gamma motor neurons.^[25]

The finding of Group A in the present study is going in the concurrence with the study done by Dafda et. al. (2022); and Dabhi et al. (2020). According to the authors, the Hold-Relax Stretching improves flexibility by relaxing the contractile component of muscles, while static stretching increases elasticity of the non-contractile viscoelastic component.^[10,19,26-28]

Dabhi et al. noticed the Hold-Relax Stretching technique helpful to relax hypertonic muscle in stroke patients^[19] and recommended its use to treat spasticity in hemiplegic patients.^[28]

In Group B, Tendinous Pressure technique was found significantly effective on calf muscle tone. The pre-intervention mean of Modified Ashworth's Scale score of group B was 1.63 and post-

intervention 1.23 respectively. (p value <0.001). This result is supporting the studies done by Ali Shaukat, et. al. (2017); Gardas, et. al. (2020); Ali Shaukat, et. al. (2017); Marathe et. al. (2020) and Panda, et. al. (2023).^[15,12,15,13] Manual pressure applied to the tendinous insertion exerts a constant stimulus to the peripheral receptors of both agonist and antagonist musculature which produces a longer lasting H-reflex inhibition. Gardas, et. al provides good evidence of anti spastic effect of circumferential pressure by sphygmomanometer on wrist and plantar flexors.

Ali S. et. al. (2017) observed 8 weeks intervention of sustained stretching helpful to reduce spasticity in 5 stroke patients aged between 45 and 65).^[15]

Panda O, et. al.(2023) and Maratheet. Al. (2020) found Tendinous Pressure technique more effective than Myofascial Release Technique to reduce spasticity in stroke patients. Researchers found both techniques capable for reducing spasticity but tendinous pressure technique was superior to Myofascial Release technique).^[14,13]

The current study found Hold-Relax Stretching technique more effective than Tendinous Pressure technique on calf muscle tone in patients with stroke. Similar result was noticed in the study conducted by Dafda, et. al. (2021).^[15] They noticed more reduction in the elbow flexor spasticity of stroke patients by Hold-Relax Stretching technique as compared to Static Stretching. It is because, during isometric contraction of the muscles in their lengthened range leads to production of great amount of tension which may stimulate the GTOs in the muscles which causes increase in inhibitory input causing muscles to reflexively relax.^[26-30] Autogenic inhibition causes a muscle to relax after more than six seconds of continuous contraction, in the present study isometric contraction was given for 10 seconds.^[17]

Hong et. al. (2020) investigated effect Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation (PNF) stretching, joint mobilization, and Positional Stretching through incline board standing in 45 stroke patients (15 in each group). Authors recommended PNF Hold-Relax Stretching technique as an effective intervention method to increase the dorsiflexion of the ankle joint and decrease the calf muscle tone. Among these three methods, PNF stretching involves reciprocal dominance in the Golgi tendon organ, which responds to muscle extension and contraction. It applies passive stretching and active exercise in harmony by simultaneously suppressing and promoting reflexes.^[31]

Conclusion: The findings of the current study showed positive impact of hold relax stretching technique and tendinous pressure technique in reducing calf muscle tone along with conventional positional stretching in stroke patients. A clear significant difference was observed between pre and post intervention Modified Ashworth's Scale score of calf muscle in stroke patients. However, Hold-Relax Stretching technique was noticed more beneficial than Tendinous Pressure technique.

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